

LEGAL AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATION: THE ROLE OF LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LAW

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Law and language, the harmony between them, the definition of these relations are important in the development of any country, in maintaining law and order in the state, in raising legal awareness and legal culture in society. Because the concepts of state independence, state and law, state language are intertwined are closely related events. It is impossible to have others without one.

Therefore, the development of law and language plays an important role in the development of society, and the development of society or law is reflected in the development of language. This lays a great foundation for the development of the state and society, as well as the development of law and linguistics.

Law arose on the basis of the objective necessity of human society. There is a need in society for legal norms that determine the rights of citizens and ensure discipline. Accordingly, a human society has emerged, and there are laws that reflect the rules of that society.

Language is the most important means of conveying information and exchanging ideas. "Language is a unit of preparation for all members of a society, prepared by generations (previous generations), common to all, that is, mandatory for adoption and use, serving the formation, expression and other purposes of thought, and defining the interconnection and interdependence of these units. is a set of rules"[1].

Language vividly expresses ideas, feelings, thoughts (including legal norms). It allows humanity to exchange information with the present, the past, the future, to preserve the spiritual riches accumulated by humanity.

In general, language and law are one of the most ancient social phenomena of mankind. With the advent of man came the need for communication. Then, with the decision of society, the law came into being. Accordingly, language is much older than law.

While language allows a person to exchange information (communicative), law defines the rights and freedoms of every citizen, and governs social relations in society.

Defining the relationship between law and language is extremely difficult. Because they are interconnected and interrelated on the one hand, and on the other hand, they have different aspects of each other because they belong to relatively independent fields. But even so, many jurists and linguists have tried to define this relationship.

When it comes to the functions of law and language in social life, it should be emphasized that they perform exactly the same function as managing human behavior.

While language is the most important means of human communication, it

in a sense serves the function of controlling human behavior. The famous German scientist Wilhelm Humboldt (1767-1835) wrote about this, defining the place of language in the relationship between society and man: "Language is a means of self-knowledge, understanding and, in a sense, control of the individual." [2] Indeed, as a result of language, people think and control their actions.

It should be noted that the main task of law is to regulate social relations in society, as well as to manage human behavior. Apparently, language and law have certain similarities in terms of their functions in society. Therefore, along with the development of legal science, the legal language should be improved, new means of expression should be created to make legal norms understandable to the public, legal terms should be separated from time to time, obsolete words and phrases that hinder the development of law should be removed. With the development of law, the language of law must be gradually improved.

The role of language in the development of law. In the development of society, it is extremely important to clearly define the position of language in relation to law, as well as to determine the relationship between law and language, the relationship between them.

From this point of view, from time immemorial, lawyers have wondered whether the word is the only means of conveying legal norms to citizens, whether it is possible to express it by other scientific or practical means. To this question the jurist F. Lassal responds that it is unnatural not to express the law in words, but in some cases it can be conveyed to the minds of people even with some symbolic signs (such as road signs) [3].

Contrary to this idea, lawyers believe that such symbolic signs - tables, pictures, music - can establish legal relations, not legal doctrines [4].

Indeed, this view is so correct that legal doctrines cannot and cannot be expressed by such means. These tools only perform the function of conveying some legal information. In the 5th century BC, the famous ancient Greek historian Herodotus showed that when King Darius of Iran marched into the Scythian land, the Scythian king sent him an envoy with a gift of a bird, a mouse, a frog, five bows and other valuables. The Persians themselves will have to understand the meaning of this gift. Qubra, one of Darius's courtiers, explains this: "If you, the Persians, do not fly to the sky like a bird, do not hide underground like mice, or do not cross a swamp like a frog, you will die from these arrows and will not be able to return." [5]

Apparently, some objects, symbolic symbols, can also be a means of conveying legal information, but even so, they can never replace language. Language is the existence, the past, the future of humanity. There can be no civil society without language, including law.

As mentioned above, it is not logical to assume that legal norms can be conveyed to citizens through non-verbal symbolic symbols. Let these legal norms be conveyed by various means without language. In observation, do both the transmitter and the receiver of this medium think through language and draw certain conclusions?

So, it can be said that without language, legal norms can never be

conveyed to citizens. Language is a "living" condition of this right. In general, the legal literature emphasizes the uniqueness of the role of language in the development of law, but it is not clear and complete indication of the specific functions of language in the development of law. The legal literature on these issues states: "Language performs two important functions in relation to law. First, language is a lawyer's tool for thinking; the second is to convey the lawyer's order to the participants in the social relationship"[6]. Even this definition of the functions of language in the development of law, in our view, does not fully cover the essence of the issue. Because the above definition is given not in terms of the whole content and essence of the law, but rather in terms of legislation. Accordingly, there are other functions of language in the development of law that have been overlooked by the authors. In our opinion, language plays the following five main roles in the development of law:

- transmission of legal knowledge from generation to generation;
- a means of mutual exchange of views between lawyers;
- A tool for legal thinking;
- represents the will of the legislator;
- conveys legal norms to citizens.

Thus, in the development of language law: first, the transmission of legal knowledge from generation to generation; second, a means of mutual exchange of views between lawyers; third, a means of legal reasoning; fourth, to express the will of the legislator; fifth, it is responsible for conveying legal norms to citizens.

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